

Deliverable D5.3a

Mechanistic analyses via the COVID-19 Disease Map

Project Title (grant agreement No)	BY-COVID Grant Agreement 101046203		
Project Acronym (EC Call)	BY-COVID		
WP No & Title	WP5: A continuously evolving demonstrator project feeding the changing research questions that surface during an ongoing pandemic to solutions		
WP Leaders	Nina Van Goethem (Sciensano) Enrique Bernal Delgado (IACS)		
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary	5 - UNILU		
Contractual delivery date	30/11/2023	Actual Delivery date	26/07/2024
Delayed	Yes - new deadline agreed with PO		
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable	UNILU, INMI, EU-OS (Fraunhofer ITMP), Euro-BioImaging, Erasmus MC		
Authors	Marek Ostaszewski (UNILU) ORCID: 0000-0003-1473-370X Francesco Messina (INMI) ORCID: 0000-0001-8076-7217		
Contributors	Aastha Mathur, Isabel Kemmer (Euro-BioImaging), Philip Gribbon (Fraunhofer ITMP), Andrew Stubbs, Helena Rasche (Erasmus MC)		
Acknowledgements (not grant participants)	Matti Hoch from the University of Rostock, the Organisers of the ELIXIR BioHackathon 2020		
Reviewers	Laura Portell (BSC/UPF), Erdina Ene (BBMRI), Henning Hermjakob (EBI) Ilaria Colussi (BBMRI-ERIC), Louiza Kalokairinou (ELIXIR Hub) - ELSI compliance		

Log of changes

Date	Mvm	Who	Description
22/11/2023		Marek Ostaszewski (UNILU)	Initial version
24/11/2023		Francesco Messina (INMI)	Updated version
23/01/2024		Marek Ostaszewski (UNILU)	Addressing reviewers' remarks

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Table of contents

1. Executive Summary	3
1.1 Deliverable Scope	4
1.2 Work accomplished	4
1.3 Conclusion	4
2. Contribution towards project objectives	5
Objective 1	5
Objective 2	5
Objective 3	6
Objective 4	6
Objective 5	6
3. Methods	7
3.1 Deliverable scope	7
3.1.1 Relationship with other WPs	8
3.2 Methodology	8
4. Description of work accomplished	9
4.1 Visualisation of microscopy data	9
4.1.1 BioImage Archive dataset of drug repurposing analysis	9
4.1.2 EMPIAR set of virus protein structures	9
4.2 Visualisation of proteomics data for SARS-CoV-2 strains	10
4.3 Galaxy workflow for reproducible omics visualisation	11
5. Results	12
6. Discussion	13
7. Conclusions	13
8. Next steps	14
9. Impact	15
10. References	15

1. Executive Summary

1.1 Deliverable Scope

In this Deliverable, we demonstrated the use of datasets and workflows in BY-COVID to better understand the mechanisms of SARS-CoV-2, supporting research towards preventive or therapeutic approaches. To this end, we connected different data sources from the BY-COVID partners and the public domain to a systems biology knowledge repository of COVID-19 molecular mechanisms - the COVID-19 Disease Map¹.

1.2 Work accomplished

First, in collaboration with colleagues from Work Package 2, we developed two visualisation plugins for the COVID-19 Disease Map. These two plugins display in the Map i) drug repurposing results of a high-throughput drug screen and ii) a collection of virus-specific protein structures reconstructed from microscopy imaging. The visualisations are a result of connecting to SARS-CoV-2 datasets on the BioImage Archive of drug repurposing analysis² and the Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive (EMPIAR) set of virus protein structures³.

Second, we developed data overlays for a public proteomics dataset representing infection by three different SARS-CoV-2 strains in the Calu-3 cell line (Mezler et al. 2023⁴).

Finally, collaborating with colleagues from Work Package 4, we prototyped a Galaxy workflow capable of visualising transcriptomic data on the COVID-19 Disease Map.

1.3 Conclusion

With this work, we were able to demonstrate components of a workflow, allowing us to:

- Process SARS-CoV-2 omics data relevant to virus mechanisms in a streamlined way with a Galaxy workflow
- Visually interpret the data on the COVID-19 Disease Map
- Enrich the interpretation of the results by connected microscopy data

This proof of concept can be extended to cover individual BY-COVID data sources and datasets in the COVID-19 Data portal. Extension of source material, construction of further

¹ COVID-19 Disease Map: <https://fairdomhub.org/projects/190> [accessed 24/01/2024]

² BioImage Archive: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/bioimages/studies/S-BIAD29> [accessed 24/01/2024]

³ EMPIAR: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/emdb/search/database:EMPIAR%20AND%20SARS-CoV-2> [accessed 24/01/2024]

⁴ Mezler et al: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcpro.2023.100537> [accessed 24/01/2024]

workflows, and availability of new content in the COVID-19 Disease Map will increase the range of possible analyses and establish research hypotheses.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Enable storage, sharing, access, analysis and processing of research data and other digital research objects from outbreak research	1. A research data management practice in European research infrastructures that drives discovery, access and reuse of outbreak data and directly links experimental data from HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 transnational access projects into the COVID-19 Data Portal.	No
	2. Workflows and processing pipelines that integrate transparent quality management and provenance and are openly shared.	Yes
	3. Research infrastructures on-target training so that users can exploit the platform.	Yes
	4. Engagement so stakeholders (RI, national centres, policymakers, intergovernmental organisations, funders and end-users) incorporate FAIR and open data in infectious disease guidelines and forward planning.	No
Objective 2 Mobilise and expose viral and human infectious disease data from national centres	1. A comprehensive registry of available data with established procedures to collate data governance models, metadata descriptions and access mechanisms in a pandemic scenario.	No
	2. Mechanisms for the initial discovery across data sources based on available metadata at the reference collection.	No
	3. Demonstrate transnational linking of real-world data from national surveillance, healthcare, registries, and social science data that allow the assessment of variants to serve epidemiology and public health research needs.	No
	4. Demonstrate assessment of emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants against data generated in the ongoing European VACCELERATE clinical trials project to investigate vaccine efficacy.	No

<p>Objective 3</p> <p>Link FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19</p>	<p>1. A platform that links normative pathogen genomes and variant representations to research cohorts and mechanistic studies to understand the biomolecular determinants of variant response on patient susceptibility and disease pathways.</p> <p>2. An open and extensible metadata framework adopted cross-domain that supports comprehensive indexing of the infectious disease sources based on mappings across sources and research domains.</p> <p>3. A provenance framework for researchers and policy-makers that enables trust in results and credit to data submitters, workflow contributors and participant sources.</p>	<p>Yes</p> <p>No</p> <p>No</p>
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>Develop digital tools and data analytics for pandemic and outbreak preparedness, including tracking genomics variations of SARS-CoV-2 and identifying new variants of concern</p>	<p>1. Broad uptake of viral <i>Data Hubs</i> across Europe delivers an order-of-magnitude increase in open viral variant detection and sharing.</p> <p>2. Infrastructure and quality workflows are mobilised and shared to produce open, normative variant data incorporated into national and regional data systems and decision-making.</p>	<p>No</p> <p>No</p>
<p>Objective 5</p> <p>Contribute to the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and European Health Data Space (EHDS)</p>	<p>1. Guidelines and procedures for FAIR data management and access will be established, building on the work of other guideline-producing consortia such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), the 1Mio Genomes Initiative (1MG) and the Beyond One Million Genomes project (B1MG).</p> <p>2. Services, software, protocols, guidelines and other research objects that are openly accessible for reuse by the EOSC Association and the community at large as a foundation for European preparedness for infectious diseases, leveraging developments in EOSC-Life, SSHOC, EOSC-Future, EGI-ACE and other EOSC projects.</p>	<p>No</p> <p>Yes</p>

	3. Alignment (policy and implementation routes) will have been achieved between the data governance strategies for routinely collected health data in the EHDS initiative, including the TEHDAS Joint Action and future EHDS Pilot Actions.	No
	4. To empower national centres to build capacity and train platform users and data providers (e.g., from life, social or health sciences), and with experts from across partner institutions collaborating to create training materials for the identified gaps and to exchange experiences and knowledge.	No

3. Methods

3.1 Deliverable scope

This Deliverable aims to demonstrate the use of omics molecular data mobilised by the BY-COVID Consortium in supporting research on molecular mechanisms of SARS-CoV-2 in a reproducible and scalable way. Therefore, we focus on processing and visualising gene or protein expression data from human subjects or model systems and on relevant knowledge repositories and databases that support exploring and explaining such data.

In this Deliverable, we use the COVID-19 Disease Map (Ostaszewski et al. 2021⁵) for visualisation and interpretation of molecular data. Disease maps are diagrammatic representations of disease mechanisms, developed for a given condition⁶. The COVID-19 Disease Map is developed by a community of over 200 researchers, creating an opportunity for BY-COVID to use a relevant resource of SARS-CoV-2 mechanisms and raise visibility in the research community.

The datasets in this Deliverable were selected to allow collaboration with other work package partners and showcase a range of possible use of molecular data mobilised in BY-COVID.

3.1.1 Relationship with other WPs

- **WP2:** Aastha Mathur, Isabel Kemmer (Euro-BioImaging), Philip Gribbon (Fraunhofer ITMP)
Interfacing with imaging databases and datasets of SARS-CoV-2 high throughput screens and microscopy protein structures

⁵ COVID-19 Disease Map: <https://doi.org/10.15252/msb.202110851> [accessed 24/01/2024]

⁶ Disease maps: <https://disease-maps.org> [accessed 24/01/2024]

Integration/Harmonization with/of COVID-19 Knowledge Graph⁷

- **WP4:** Andrew Stubbs, Helena Rasche (Erasmus MC)
Construction of a Galaxy workflow for transcriptomics processing and visualisation in the COVID-19 Disease Map

3.2 Methodology

Omics data

Transcriptomics (Togami et al. 2022⁸) and proteomics (Mezler et al. 2023⁹) datasets come from the public domain; lists of differentially expressed molecules are calculated as suggested by original publications.

Visualisation

Data directly visualised in the COVID-19 Disease Map (Ostaszewski et al. 2021¹⁰), using the data overlay functionality of the MINERVA Platform¹¹.

Plugins

Plugins were developed using the MINERVA Plugins Architecture¹², and the plugin connecting the Galaxy workflow with the COVID-19 Disease Map was developed by Matti Hoch from the University of Rostock based on the work during the ELIXIR BioHackathon in 2020, see:

<https://github.com/elixir-europe/BioHackathon-projects-2020/tree/master/projects/27>.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Visualisation of microscopy data

In collaboration with partners from **Work Package 2**, we have mapped two microscopy datasets to the COVID-19 Disease Map (C19DMap) and visualised links between the data and the contents of the C19DMap as loadable plugins. WP2 partners provided specifications of both datasets and evaluated the performance and utility of the plugins, and together we developed the strategy on which aspects of the dataset could be visualised and how.

⁷ COVID-19 Knowledge Graph <https://github.com/Fraunhofer-ITMP/BY-COVID-KG> [accessed 24/01/2024]

⁸ Transcriptomics: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omtn.2022.07.005> [accessed 24/01/2024]

⁹ Proteomics: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcpro.2023.100537> [accessed 24/01/2024]

¹⁰ COVID-19 Disease Map: <https://doi.org/10.15252/msb.202110851> [accessed 24/01/2024]

¹¹ MINERVA Platform: <https://doi.org/10.1038/npisba.2016.20> [accessed 24/01/2024]

¹² MINERVA Plugins Architecture: <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz286> [accessed 24/01/2024]

4.1.1 BioImage Archive dataset of drug repurposing analysis

We have mapped the microscopy data from a drug repurposing experiment in the Caco-2 cell line, available at <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/bioimages/studies/S-BIAD29>. The dataset describes a high-throughput microscopy screen of compounds applied to SARS-CoV-2 infected cells. The plugin displays the screened compounds in a table, and their predicted targets are on-the-fly displayed in the C19DMap. Related microscopy data can be accessed from the screen via a download button. The plugin was loaded to the C19DMap and is accessible directly from the user interface. The code of the plugin is available in a dedicated, open GitLab repository¹³, together with the instructions for use. Example of use is demonstrated in the figure below.

4.1.2 EMPIAR set of virus protein structures

We set out to map SARS-CoV-2 protein structures to proteins in the C19DMap. Therefore we have compiled a list of openly available structures solved by electron microscopy of complexes between SARS-CoV-2 proteins and human proteins from the Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive (EMPIAR). We mapped the components of these complexes to the molecules in the C19DMap in a visualisation plugin to browse them in the C19DMap and display images of the structures directly in the C19DMap. The code of the plugin is available in a dedicated, open GitLab repository¹⁴, together with the instruction of use. The plugin was also loaded to the C19DMap and is accessible directly from the user interface. Example of use is demonstrated in the figure below.

¹³ GitLab repository - BioImage Archive:

<https://gitlab.lcsb.uni.lu/minerva/plugins/by-covid-bioimage-archive> [accessed 24/01/2024]

¹⁴ GitLab repository - EMPIAR: <https://gitlab.lcsb.uni.lu/minerva/plugins/by-covid-empiar> [accessed 24/01/2024]

4.2 Visualisation of proteomics data for SARS-CoV-2 strains

We have developed data overlays for a public proteomics dataset representing SARS-CoV-2 infection in lung cell lines (Mezler et al. 2023¹⁵), while the raw data are available at <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride/archive/projects/PXD037265>. In particular, this dataset reports the LC-MS/MS proteomics data of the Calu-3 cell line infected with three main SARS-CoV-2 variants, B.1, Delta and Omicron BA.1, collected at different time points (6, 12 and 24 hours post-infection - hpi). DEPs for each variant only for 24 hpi were adapted to build overlays, following the authors' inclusion criteria, which are available on C19DMap. These data overlays were uploaded to the C19DMap to demonstrate how combining data and systems biology diagrams helps investigate potential strain-specific mechanisms. The figure below illustrates the three data overlays visualised across the C19DMap. A summary of differential expression profiles (background image) indicates pathway-level changes and detailed visualisation is available for individual proteins, as shown for Orf3a protein interactions (inset).

¹⁵ Mezler et al: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcpro.2023.100537> [accessed 24/01/2024]

These data overlays are openly available for all users of the C19DMap¹⁶ (<https://covid19map.elixir-luxembourg.org/minerva/?x=2857&y=1346&zoom=4&searchCoordinates=418,2509,931,4&overlays=563&>).

4.3 Galaxy workflow for reproducible omics visualisation

In collaboration with colleagues from **Work Package 4**, we prototyped a Galaxy workflow capable of visualising transcriptomic data on the COVID-19 Disease Map. Helena Rasche (Erasmus MC) developed a Galaxy workflow processing a publicly available dataset (Togami et al. 2022, [10.1016/j.omtn.2022.07.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omtn.2022.07.005)). The workflow calculates statistically significant, differentially expressed genes to be displayed in the C19DMap. The workflow then launches a dedicated visualisation plugin developed by Matti Hoch from the University of Rostock. The final result can be observed in the figure below, with differential expression visualised in the map and represented as a table in the plugin area (right panel).

¹⁶ C19DMap:

<https://covid19map.elixir-luxembourg.org/minerva/?x=2857&y=1346&zoom=4&searchCoordinates=418,2509,931,4&overlays=563&> [accessed 24/01/2024]

The workflow is already registered in the WorkflowHub under:

- <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/688>
- <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/689>

and the documentation is under preparation, driven by Helena Rasche from WP4 (intermediate version available here <https://zenodo.org/records/10405036>).

The workflow will be described in detail in a dedicated publication that is currently in preparation.

5. Results

We were able to connect different bioinformatic resources to a dedicated knowledge repository of COVID-19 mechanisms. On the one hand, these bioinformatic databases describe specific outcomes of experimental investigations of SARS-CoV-2 proteins (drug screening, protein structures). On the other hand, we connect omics data describing a response to viral infection as a set of complex signatures on a molecular level. In both cases, their mapping to the C19DMap provides context, connecting particular host and viral molecules into a bigger picture.

By mapping proteomics data, we demonstrated how complex omics data can be used for comparison of host response to different viral strains, providing a digital representation of variant-specific infection highly consistent with the real world. This dataset was used in place of sensitive data sets mobilised in BY-COVID¹⁷; however, this process is reproducible given that proper computational workflows are in place. We propose a blueprint for reproducible workflows for future Consortium datasets and potential pandemics to support this.

¹⁷ 'Datasets mobilised in BY-COVID' means, in this context, data related to the patient readouts, e.g. transcriptomic or genomic readouts.

Importantly, all results mentioned above operate on open code and open datasets under permissive licences, enabling reuse.

6. Discussion

In pandemic research, a direct link between mobilised data and their interpretation is necessary to generate scientific hypotheses, leading to the discovery of preventive or treatment measures. Molecular data (omics) are complex and difficult to analyse because they are multidimensional, noisy, and potentially carry sensitive information. For that reason, reproducible computational pipelines are needed to process and aggregate omics data. Then, they can be projected on various bioinformatic resources for interpretation.

Systems biology diagrams support such interpretation by visual analytics or more advanced computational approaches.

Here, we explored the components necessary to establish such a link. We have demonstrated the utility of visualising multiple omics data on the C19DMap to identify strain-specific mechanisms. These data, connected with entries in relevant databases (drug repurposing, viral protein structures), offer a better interpretation. Such a bridge between data producers and the research community is needed to make the most of the findings, review them and act on the hypotheses.

Notably, many steps in the workflow discussed above rely on user interactions with a graphical interface (plugins, visual exploration). While human vision is a powerful tool for analysing complex patterns, it requires reproducibility. The Galaxy framework addresses this challenge; nevertheless, clear instructions and training are needed to ensure reproducible results from such a multi-component workflow.

It should be emphasised that the current scope of work is restricted to a single dataset for demonstration purposes. It can be further extended to cover resources like Expression Atlas¹⁸. However, given the limited amount of our resources, and the scope of our work package, we focused on building scenarios of possible use cases. Another approach would be to use the published workflow (see WorkflowHub links in Section 4) and use it with another bulk RNASeq dataset.

7. Conclusions

We have delivered demonstrator cases showing workflow components for exploring molecular mechanisms of COVID-19 and its feasibility. The code and data are available in the open domain, allowing review and further implementation of the components and their connections.

¹⁸ Expression Atlas: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gxa/home> [accessed 24/01/2024]

More work is required for a closer integration of resources. While the plugin architecture of the MINERVA Platform allows flexible integration of data sources, their use is not automated as in the case of the Galaxy workflow. Furthermore, while using cases based on open data was sufficient as demonstrators at this stage, exploring BY-COVID Data Hubs as data providers is necessary to complement the workflow.

Collaboration between WPs was critical to understand data modalities and to deliver the planned functionalities. Planning similar efforts in future pandemics should involve horizontal use cases, where data from selected sources is intended for particular analytical use and guided there.

8. Next steps

The following steps are planned for the work described here:

- Publication of the Galaxy workflow - based on the discussed open data, we will submit a publication describing our work and its outcomes
- Documentation of the workflows in the IDTk - addressing the need for training, we plan to submit one or more entries describing the workflow to the Immune Disease Toolkit.
- Further integration of the Consortium data - we will monitor the progress of BY-COVID and integrate omics input from Data Hubs if available.
- Development of bioinformatic pipeline for proteomics data analysis to report other omics results to the COVID-19 Disease Maps.
- Sharing of genomic variability data on the COVID-19 Data Portal. These data relate to current circulating SARS-CoV-2 variants from clinical samples (nasopharyngeal swabs, BALF) and it will be submitted to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) on Bioprojects dedicated for BY-COVID project (PRJNA1004285¹⁹) and (PRJNA1031143²⁰). This activity of genomic data collection at INMI has already been reported in Gruber et al. 2023 and Rueca et al. 2023, [10.3390/biom13101538](https://doi.org/10.3390/biom13101538) and [10.3390/v15112192](https://doi.org/10.3390/v15112192) respectively.
- As a possible perspective, we plan to design in vitro experiments on new variant infections, reporting the updated "omics" response data on C19DMap.
- Planning of RNAseq/proteomics data sharing from in vitro experiments of infections with MonkeyPox through the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), as well as, if possible, other highly contagious viral pathogens.
- Planning the integration of further microscopy data types and datasets

¹⁹ PRJNA1004285: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA1004285> [accessed 24/01/2024]

²⁰ PRJNA1031143: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA1031143> [accessed 24/01/2024]

9. Impact

With this work, we studied the feasibility of interconnecting different resources within the BY-COVID Consortium with the public domain repositories. Such study is important in preparedness for future pandemics to enable fast-track use of omics data for biomedical research. We managed to highlight the necessary components for such a fast-track release:

- Horizontal use cases for molecular data from viral pathogens and human hosts.
- Identification of public domain repositories.
- Engagement of data controllers to identify interfaces and possibilities of use.

10. References

- Metzler M, Tharyan RG, Klann K, Grikscheit K, Bojkova D, Cinatl J, Tascher G, Ciesek S, Münch C. SARS-CoV-2 Variants Show Different Host Cell Proteome Profiles With Delayed Immune Response Activation in Omicron-Infected Cells. *Mol Cell Proteomics*. 2023 May;22(5):100537. doi: 10.1016/j.mcpro.2023.100537. Epub 2023 Mar 30. PMID: 37001587; PMCID: PMC10060015.
- Togami Y, Matsumoto H, Yoshimura J, Matsubara T, Ebihara T, Matsuura H, Mitsuyama Y, Kojima T, Ishikawa M, Sugihara F, Hirata H, Okuzaki D, Ogura H. Significance of interferon signaling based on mRNA-microRNA integration and plasma protein analyses in critically ill COVID-19 patients. *Mol Ther Nucleic Acids*. 2022 Sep 13;29:343-353. doi: 10.1016/j.omtn.2022.07.005. Epub 2022 Jul 13. PMID: 35855895; PMCID: PMC9278015.
- Ostaszewski M, Niarakis A, Mazein A, Kuperstein I, Phair R, Orta-Resendiz A, Singh V, Aghamiri SS, Acencio ML, Glaab E, Ruepp A, Fobo G, Montrone C, Brauner B, Frishman G, Monraz Gómez LC, Somers J, Hoch M, Kumar Gupta S, Scheel J, Borlinghaus H, Czuderna T, Schreiber F, Montagud A, Ponce de Leon M, Funahashi A, Hiki Y, Hiroi N, Yamada TG, Dräger A, Renz A, Naveez M, Bocskei Z, Messina F, Börnigen D, Fergusson L, Conti M, Rameil M, Nakonecniij V, Vanhoefer J, Schmiester L, Wang M, Ackerman EE, Shoemaker JE, Zucker J, Oxford K, Teuton J, Kocakaya E, Summak GY, Hanspers K, Kutmon M, Coort S, Eijssen L, Ehrhart F, Rex DAB, Slenter D, Martens M, Pham N, Haw R, Jassal B, Matthews L, Orlic-Milacic M, Senff-Ribeiro A, Rothfels K, Shamovsky V, Stephan R, Sevilla C, Varusai T, Ravel JM, Fraser R, Ortseifen V, Marchesi S, Gawron P, Smula E, Heirendt L, Satagopam V, Wu G, Riutta A, Golebiewski M, Owen S, Goble C, Hu X, Overall RW, Maier D, Bauch A, Gyori BM, Bachman JA, Vega C, Grouès V, Vazquez M, Porrás P, Licata L, Iannuccelli M, Sacco F, Nesterova A, Yuryev A, de Waard A, Turei D, Luna A, Babur O, Soliman S, Valdeolivas A, Esteban-Medina M, Peña-Chilet M, Rian K, Helikar T, Puniya BL, Modos D, Treveil A, Olbei M, De Meulder B, Ballereau S, Dugourd A, Naldi A, Noël V, Calzone L, Sander

C, Demir E, Korcsmaros T, Freeman TC, Augé F, Beckmann JS, Hasenauer J, Wolkenhauer O, Willighagen EL, Pico AR, Evelo CT, Gillespie ME, Stein LD, Hermjakob H, D'Eustachio P, Saez-Rodriguez J, Dopazo J, Valencia A, Kitano H, Barillot E, Auffray C, Balling R, Schneider R; COVID-19 Disease Map Community. COVID-19 Disease Map, a computational knowledge repository of virus-host interaction mechanisms. *Mol Syst Biol.* 2021 Dec;17(12):e10851. doi: 10.15252/msb.202110851. Erratum for: *Mol Syst Biol.* 2021 Oct;17(10):e10387. PMID: 34939300; PMCID: PMC8696085.

- Gawron P, Ostaszewski M, Satagopam V, Gebel S, Mazein A, Kuzma M, Zorzan S, McGee F, Otjacques B, Balling R, Schneider R. MINERVA-a platform for visualization and curation of molecular interaction networks. *NPJ Syst Biol Appl.* 2016 Sep 22;2:16020. doi: 10.1038/npjbsa.2016.20. PMID: 28725475; PMCID: PMC5516855.
- Hoksza D, Gawron P, Ostaszewski M, Smula E, Schneider R. MINERVA API and plugins: opening molecular network analysis and visualization to the community. *Bioinformatics.* 2019 Nov 1;35(21):4496-4498. doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/btz286. PMID: 31074494; PMCID: PMC6821317.
- Gruber CEM, Tucci FG, Rueca M, Mazzotta V, Gramigna G, Vergori A, Fabeni L, Berno G, Giombini E, Butera O, Focosi D, Prandi IG, Chillemi G, Nicastrì E, Vaia F, Girardi E, Antinori A, Maggi F. Treatment-Emergent Cilgavimab Resistance Was Uncommon in Vaccinated Omicron BA.4/5 Outpatients. *Biomolecules.* 2023 Oct 18;13(10):1538. doi: 10.3390/biom13101538. PMID: 37892220; PMCID: PMC10605390.
- Rueca M, Berno G, Agresta A, Spaziante M, Gruber CEM, Fabeni L, Giombini E, Butera O, Barca A, Scognamiglio P, Girardi E, Maggi F, Valli MB, Vairo F, Sars-CoV-Lazio Genomic Surveillance Study Group. Genomic and Epidemiologic Surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 in the Pandemic Period: Sequencing Network of the Lazio Region, Italy. *Viruses.* 2023 Oct 31;15(11):2192. doi: 10.3390/v15112192. PMID: 38005872; PMCID: PMC10674723.

